

On the Study of the Uptake of Strontium Tracer by Different forms of Calcium Sulphate.

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Distribution study with different morphological forms of calcium sulphate as host and strontium tracer as guest is the subject matter of study. It has been found that strontium tracer is taken by gypsum through mixed crystal formation. This gives a strong support to the claim of Lambert and Hume-Rothery as regards the existence of gypsum analogue of strontium sulphate.

It has been found that anhydrite takes up strontium tracer through mixed crystal formation. Both heterogeneous and homogeneous distribution factors come out constant under various experimental conditions. The partition factor in this case is much below unity and it is nearly independent of temperature and concentration of the guest component. It has been argued that this low partition value in case of anhydrite gives an explanation why Sr:Ca ratio is higher in sea than it is on land.

Among the alkaline earth sulphates different hydrates are known in the case of calcium. Any hydrate of strontium sulphate is of doubtful existence. Anhydrous calcium sulphate (anhydrite) which also occurs in nature has got morphological parameters different from other alkaline earth sulphates like those of barium, strontium and radium². But traces of strontium have been always detected in anhydrite. Isomorphous replacement is therefore expected in such cases. A study on the uptake of strontium tracer by different forms of calcium sulphate has been undertaken with the following aims to gather evidences in regard to (a) the mechanism of uptakes whether it is through mixed crystal formation or adsorption, (b) the existence of unknown dihydrate of strontium sulphate, and (c) any general findings on geochemical occurrences of calcium and strontium.

EXPERIMENTAL

Calcium chloride used in the investigation was of E. Merck (gr. reagent) quality. Sulphuric acid, hydrochloric acid, strontium nitrate were of analar variety. Carrier-free strontium tracer⁹⁰ was supplied as SrCl₂ in dilute hydrochloric acid by the Atomic Energy Establishment of India. A few drops from this was taken and a stock solution was made in hydrochloric acid (acidity. 1*N*). Aliquots of this stock solution were used in our study. A stock solution of calcium chloride in dilute hydrochloric acid, 0.5 molar was made. It was observed that calcium sulphate separates out on the addition of 2*N* sulphuric acid. But the separation of calcium sulphate does not take place immediately. On stirring for some time crystals appear. The system as such gives us the advantage of crystallisation from a homogeneous solution. Variations in the extent of crystallisation was made by addition of different quantities of sulphuric acid. Description of a typical experiment will clarify the procedure

1. Walter Huokol, "Structural Chemistry of Inorganic compounds". By Elsevier Publishing Company, 1951, p. 720.

adopted by us. Calcium chloride solution from the stock was taken in L-shaped tube fitted with standard joints. These were clamped to a shaking system. The solution was made 1N in acidity by addition of hydrochloric acid. Strontium activity was then added. It was then kept in a thermostat. Another flask containing 2N sulphuric acid was also kept at the same bath. A known volume of the acid was added to calcium chloride. The system was then closed by stoppers and shaken at the thermostat temperature with a mechanical arrangement having about 60-70 vibrations per minute for some time for complete breakdown of supersaturation. It was observed that crystals start to separate in about five minutes. A known volume of the solution was then pipetted out by a mechanical arrangement. The pipette had a filter paper cap tied at the delivery end to prevent any solid matter entering. Calcium was estimated by evaporating a portion of the solution with sulphuric acid and weighing as anhydrous calcium sulphate CaSO_4 . Sr^{90} was associated with Sr^{90} . This decays into Y^{90} which is a β emitter (3 days).

Separation of Yttrium :—

To the portion of the solution about 50 mg of natural yttrium was added. It was precipitated with carbon dioxide free ammonia. The precipitate after washing was dissolved in hydrochloric acid and some calcium chloride was added as hold-back carrier and yttrium hydroxide was reprecipitated. The filtrates of the two operations were combined together and measurement of strontium activity was made by a glass counter. That yttrium hydroxide did not carry any strontium was tested by determining the yttrium half-life. In the case of a higher pH medium, calcium chloride solution containing strontium tracer was neutralised by ammonia free from carbon dioxide. The approximately desired pH was thus obtained. Calcium sulphate was precipitated by the addition of ammonium sulphate and the pH in question was finally determined from the solution by a Beckman G pH meter. The distribution coefficients λ and D were calculated from following expressions:—

$$D \left(\frac{\text{Tracer}}{\text{Carrier}} \right)_{\text{solution}} = \left(\frac{\text{Tracer}}{\text{Carrier}} \right)_{\text{solid}} ; \quad \lambda \left[\frac{\text{Initial carrier}}{\text{Carrier in soln.}} \right] = \left[\frac{\text{Initial tracer}}{\text{Tracer in soln.}} \right]$$

Data are given in tables and figures.

TABLE I

On the study of the uptake of strontium tracer by calcium sulphate at different temperatures.

Nature of host component.	Temperature °C	pH=0.1		λ	D.
		Ca pptd.	Up take of Sr		
Gypsum	15	35.5%	23.9%	.56	.60
		71.3	50.8	.57	.41
		80.8	60.5	.56	.36
				Average	.56
"	25	52.5	31.3	.50	.41
		66.6	41.9	.49	.36
		77.5	51.0	.48	.30
				Average	.51

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TABLE I (contd.)

Nature of host component	Temperature °C	Ca pptd.	Uptake of Sr	λ	D.
"	33	61.5%	26.6%	.41	.32
		68.8	41.7	.46	.32
		75.3	45.6	.44	.27
		77.1	48.7	.45	
		Average		.44	
"	37	47.1	24.8	.43	.37
		60.3	33.7	.44	.33
		73.2	40.2	.47	.31
		74.0	44.4	.44	.28
		Average		.44	
Anhydrite	45	49.1	20.0	.38	.26
		54.7	26.5	.39	.30
		60.5	29.3	.37	.27
		Average		.38	
"	55	38.3	19.4	.32	.27
		48.4	18.3	.31	.24
		59.5	24.5	.31	.22
		65.1	32.8	.38	.26
		Average		.33	
"	65	41.5	17.7	.35	.30
		45.8	16.4	.29	.23
		54.0	25.9	.39	.30
		65.9	30.4	.34	.33
		Average		.34	
"	74	21.1	7.4	.32	.30
		30.0	18.8	.32	.28
		40.1	14.3	.30	.24
		Average		.31	
*Gypsum	15	30.0	14.6	.44	.40
		59.8	33.9	.45	.34
		76.1	46.1	.43	.37
		85.3	57.6	.45	.33
		Average		.44	
*Anhydrite	45	43.3	9.4	.17	.14
		57.5	20.5	.27	.18
		67.2	23.5	.24	.16
		70.0	26.2	.25	.15
		Average		.25	.16
* "	55	35.6	7.6	.18	.15
		47.8	12.8	.21	.16
		63.9	21.0	.24	.16
		Average		.21	.16

TABLE I (contd.)

Nature of host component	Temperature °C	Ca pptd.	Uptake of Sr	λ	D.
*Anhydrite	65	32.2%	0.6%	.18	.16
		42.6	11.5	.22	.17
		50.0	14.0	.24	.17
		58.0	18.5	.23	.16
			Average	.16	—
**Unstable form of gypsum	33	20.0	24.8	0.80	.77
		40.2	35.0	0.65	.57
		68.7	47.8	0.56	.42

*The internally formed crystals were shaken for three days. In case where there were closer agreement average values have been recorded in the table (vide discussion).

**In the solution calcium chloride in hydrochloric acid ($\approx 1N$) containing strontium tracer and sulphuric acid was slowly added. Supersaturation was suddenly broken by quick stirring the homogeneous solution. Separation of the solution phase was done within five minutes.

TABLE II

On the study of the uptake of strontium tracer by calcium sulphate at different pH

Nature of host component.	Temp°C	pH	Ca pptd.	Uptake of Sr.	λ	D
Anhydrite	55	0.1			0.33	[vide table-I]
,,	55	1.5	21.1%	0.0%	0.40	0.37
			46.4	25.8	.48	.40
			65.5	33.9	.30	.27
			84.0	55.0	.44	.23
			Average	0.43	—	
,,	55	3	22.6	13.3	0.56	.33
			44.5	27.2	.54	.47
			65.6	44.3	.55	.42
			82.8	57.5	.49	.28
			Average	0.53	—	
,,	55	8.5	30.7	12.3	0.57	.54
			40.1	27.3	.52	.44
			72.7	49.8	.53	.37
			Average	0.54	—	
Gypsum	15	1.5	35.0	34.2	0.97	.96
			57.7	52.2	.86	.80
			66.8	65.8	.97	.95
			Average	0.94	—	
*Anhydrite	55	0.8	19.2	11.7	0.58	.58
			31.2	18.8	.56	.50
			64.6	48.1	.62	.50
			75.7	61.0	.68	.51
			Average	0.61	—	
*Gypsum	15	8.0	12.5	15.3	1.2	1.3
			35.5	30.0	0.84	0.81
			56.6	51.5	.89	.86
			77.6	62.6	.86	.48

*The internally formed crystals were shaken for three days. In case where there were closer agreement average values have been recorded in the table (vide discussion).

TABLE III

On the study of the uptake of strontium tracer by calcium sulphate in presence of inactive strontium.

Nature of host	Temp. °C.	Amount of Sr.SO ₄ ml.	Ca pptd.	Uptake of Sr.	λ	D
Gypsum	33	0.112 mg	44.6%	29.5%	.60	.52
			69.6	49.5	.67	.43
			70.8	55.0	.66	.38
			Average		.67	
,,	33	0.0112 mg	46.1	24.4	.45	.38
			55.7	30.1	.44	.34
			65.7	35.8	.42	.29
			Average		.44	
Anhydrite	57	0.112 mg	35.0	10.8	.27	.23
			44.7	20.5	.29	.28
			62.8	26.0	.31	.21
			Average		.31	
,,	57	0.0112	33.4	11.5	.30	.26
			56.1	23.3	.32	.24
			63.5	32.6	.39	.28
			Average		.34	
*Anhydrite	57	.112	32.2	8.3	.22	.19
			55.2	15.9	.21	.15
			65.8	22.4	.24	.15
			Average		.18	

*The internally formed crystals were shaken for three days. In case where there were closer agreement average values have been recorded in the table (vide discussion).

N.B.

In all the tables it will be observed that while finding out homogeneous distribution factor heterogeneous distribution factor also comes out constant in some cases of anhydrite. This is due to difficulties in effecting larger variations because of low uptake. But these apparent values are much lower than those arrived through normal procedure.

DISCUSSION

We now summarise the characteristics of the uptake of strontium tracers by different forms of calcium sulphate.

Gypsum:

(a) Table-1 shows that λ values in the case of monoclinic gypsum are constant. So gypsum takes some strontium tracer through mixed crystal formation. This is an evidence in support of the observation of Lambert and Hume-Rothary² that the needles which the authors observed under the microscope were the gypsum analogue of strontium sulphate. (b) λ values show a rise with the fall in temperature. High partition values are also observed at finite concentrations of the guest component. These facts are also in close agree-

2. Lambert and Hume-Rothary, *J.C.S.*, 1926, 126, 1037.

ment with the observations of Lambert and Hume-Rothary. (c) At higher pH of the medium of crystallisation partition value increases. (d) Though the uptake of the strontium tracer is through mixed crystal formation, the homogeneous distribution factor is not obeyed on prolonged equilibration in an internally formed system. The distribution remains

Study of distribution coefficient on the uptake of Sr^{90} by calcium sulphate at different temperatures

heterogeneous. This indicates that diffusion and recrystallisation in the system is a very slow process. The same fact was also observed by equilibrating gypsum (prepared externally, powdered and filtered through 120 mesh) for a period of 11 days under identical conditions as was done in the case of internally formed systems. The extent of uptake was negligibly small. (e) The unstable orthorhombic form of gypsum³ does not exercise much influence if crystallisation is done by breaking down supersaturation at a slow rate. The orthorhombic form appears only on a quick breakdown of the supersaturation and the uptake in that case has been found to follow an adsorption pattern.

Anhydrite :

(a) Tables 1 and 3 show that at temperature of 45°C and above strontium tracer is also taken up by the host component through mixed crystal formation. Both homogeneous and heterogeneous distribution factors has been found to be constant. Constancy of the distribution factors has also been verified at finite concentrations of strontium. It can be concluded that strontium is taken by anhydrite through mixed crystal formation. (b) Unlike gypsum the distribution values are nearly independent of temperature and the concentration of the guest component. (c) Partition values undergo a prominent change as it does in the case of gypsum with increase in the pH of the medium of crystallisation.

It is of interest to point out that though strontium sulphate is much more insoluble than anhydrite the partition value in this case is always much below unity. Our co-separation study with strontium sulphate as host and Ca^{45} as guest does not give any evidence of uptake of calcium by the host in question which is expected from the anomalous behaviour mentioned above. This unexpected behaviour in the uptake of strontium by anhydrite may probably help us in finding out the cause why Sr:Ca ratio is higher in sea water than it is on land.

Goldschmidt⁴ on the basis of a few analyses of anhydrite observed that Sr:Ca ratio was the same as it was in sea water whereas in gypsum the ratio is much lower. He explained the cause of enrichment of strontium in sea water as due to the escape of strontium because of gypsumisation of the anhydrites. From those analytical data it seemed that the partition values of anhydrite should be unity whereas our study under different experimental conditions sets forth a clear evidence that in whatever conditions anhydrite may carry strontium, the partition factor is far below unity and much less than it is in the case of gypsum. If the partition factor of anhydrite as host and the strontium tracer as guest would have been unity then it is expected that strontium sulphate should also take up some calcium tracers at a favourable temperature. Our co-separation study with calcium tracer (Ca^{45}) reveals that strontium sulphate does not take up any appreciable amount of calcium tracer. This is also a strong evidence in favour of the view that partition factor in these two species is not near about unity.

It will not be out of place to mention that the first solid phase that crystallises out from sea water is rather calcium carbonate. The calcite structure which is a stable form of calcium carbonate is not expected to contain much strontium for which the aragonite structure is stable. Moreover the carbonate content of sea is not high enough to account for the anomalous enrichment of the sea with strontium. From these facts it seems that the anomalous partition factor as found by us may be responsible for such enrichment.

It should also be mentioned that the solid phase which separated above 45°C under our experimental condition was assumed to be anhydrite because of the following reasons:

- (a) The partition values show a characteristic change (vide fig. 1) near about 40°C.
- (b) Solubility of calcium sulphate at different temperature as described by Chassevent⁵ also shows such a characteristic change.
- (c) A thorough study by d'Ans *et al.*⁶ also gives strong evidence that the solid phase separating above 45°C should be anhydrite.

Radioactive indicators thus help in deriving evidences in regard to unstable compounds unknown hitherto and a coseparation study also helps to clarify the observed abundances of rare elements.

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4. *Geochemistry*, Goldschmidt, Edited by Alex Muir, Oxford, 1954, p. 249.

5. Chassevent *L. Ann. Chem.* (10) 6, (1936 272, 313).

6. J d'Ans, D. Bradtschneider, H Eick and H. E. Freund, *Koll U Steinsalz*, No. 9 1955 17.